

Solid state Nd:YAG laser cutting of CFRP sheet: influence of process parameters on kerf geometry and HAZ

C. Leone¹, N. Pagano¹, V. Lopresto¹, I. De Iorio²

¹Dept. of Materials and Production Engineering, ²Dept. of Aerospace Engineering
University of Naples "Federico II", P.le Tecchio 80, 80125 Naples, Italy
claleone@unina.it, nitinol@hotmail.it, lopresto@unina.it, isadeior@unina.it

SUMMARY

Pulsed Nd:YAG laser was used in cutting operation on 1 mm CFRP plates at different cutting speed changing the pulse duration and the pulse energy. The aim was to study the process parameters influence on the kerf geometry and HAZ extension. It was found that a decrease of pulse duration allows to obtain high quality cutting and narrow HAZ.

Keywords: Carbon fibre composites, Nd:YAG laser, laser cutting, kerf geometry, HAZ.

I. INTRODUCTION

Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastic (CFRP) materials are generally used for structural applications in different fields. Even though near-net manufacturing of composite materials is possible, cutting and drilling will remain an unavoidable operations. Cutting and drilling of CFRP composites with conventional cutting methods produce tool wear, damage such as delamination and fibre pull out [1-7]. Moreover, machining is not good when very small complex shape are required. Laser cutting represents a possible alternative: it does not involve any mechanical cutting force and tool wear, thanks to the small spot laser beam that allow to realize complex shape too. However, laser cutting is based on the interaction between laser beam and the composites, that produce heat affected zone (HAZ). Thermal damage is a direct consequence of the large difference in thermal properties of the carbon fibre and the epoxy matrix [6]. In fact during the beam-material interaction, the time that elapses before the vaporisation condition for carbon fibres is larger than that for the resin. During this period, thanks to the good conductivity of the fibres, a great amount of heat is absorbed by the matrix, producing matrix burning [8]. It results that the HAZ is characterized by the presence of fibres debonded from the matrix and thermal degradation of both fibres and matrix [6]. Obviously the HAZ dimension is strictly dependent on the adopted laser source, its mode (continuous or pulsed) and the working parameters [6-12].

The use of pulsed Nd:YAG laser in cutting operation of CFRP was investigated in [13]. It was found that the high beam intensity and the better focusing behaviour of the pulsed Nd:YAG lasers lead to a smaller thermal load and so a narrow kerf and a small HAZ compared to CO₂ ones, if the right parameter combinations are adopted.

Since the HAZ and the kerf width depend on the energy release-time dependence, a strategy to decrease the HAZ and the kerf width could be the use of high pulse energy released in very short time, like in the case of short or ultra-short laser pulsed source. For this laser source, the high peak power released in short time rapidly heats the

material and directly leads to the evaporation and/or plasma [6], reducing the heat absorbed by the matrix and then the HAZ extension. This is well known in laser micro machining of metallic and ceramic materials, where the reduction of the pulse duration produces smaller thermal damage and higher precision cutting [14-16].

Aim of the work is to study the features and the performances of a 100 W lamp pumped pulsed Nd:YAG laser in cutting 1 mm in thickness CFRP laminates.

Cutting tests were carried out on a 1 mm CFRP plate obtained by autoclave cure. During the tests, different pulse durations and pulse energies were adopted. For each process condition, the maximum cutting speed was determined. Then, starting from this value, the cutting speed was reduced up to obtain spot overlap value of about 95 %.

The kerf sections of all the samples were examined by microscopic analysis measuring the top and bottom kerf width, the taper angle and the HAZ extension. At the end, the kerf geometry and the HAZ were related to the process condition.

It was found that the use of short pulse duration allows to obtain the highest cutting speed, while the HAZ extension decreases at the decreasing of both the pulse duration and the spot overlap percentage.

II. EQUIPMENT, MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

An industrial multimode pulsed Nd:YAG (Starcut 150 from ROFIN), working at the wavelength of 1064 nm, with a maximum average power of 150 W was used in the experiments. The laser allows the selection of different working parameters like the pump lamp voltage (V), the pulse frequency (F), and the pulse duration (D). The mean power (P_m), the pulse energy (E) and the pulse power (P_p) depend, for a fixed lamp voltage, on the pulse frequency and the duration.

The mean power, the pulse repetition frequency, the pulse energy and the pulse power play important roles during laser engraving, since they control the interaction between the laser beam and the material. So, in order to evaluate the efficiency of the process, laser cutting trials were carried out adopting three value of duration (1, 0.5 and 0.25 ms) and three values of pulse energy (about 0.65, 0.50 and 0.35 J). The different energy values were obtained changing the pulse frequency and the lamp voltage. In table I, the process parameters used in this study are reported together with the beam properties.

The laser beam is transmitted through five mirrors from the source to the laser head (PRECITEC AK YK52) and then it is focused by a lens with a focal length of 80 mm. In all the cutting operations the laser beam was focussed on the surface of the samples. In these conditions, the focused beam diameter, indicated by the manufacturer, is about 170 μm . Air at 10 bar of pressure and 30 l/min of flow was used as assist gas. A nozzle 0.8 mm in diameter was used.

The cutting process with a pulsed Nd:YAG laser involves on overlapping of a series of individual holes generated by each pulse as reported in figure 1. A key parameter in pulsed laser cutting is the spot overlap percentage (also called overlapping percentage) that represents the overlap between two consecutive pulses. The spot overlap percentage can be calculated by the equation 1):

$$\text{Spot overlap (\%)} = 100 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{S}{F \cdot W} \right) \quad 1)$$

where S is the cutting speed, F is the pulse repetition frequency and W is the kerf width.

For each process condition, the maximum cutting speed was determined. Then, starting from this value, the cutting speed was reduced up to obtain a spot overlap value of about 95%.

The investigated material was a 1 mm in thickness CFRP plate obtained by autoclave cure. The reinforcing material used was T400 carbon fibre. The lay-up was: 2 external plies of fabric 193 gr/mm³ each one, with 50% fibre in the warp and weft directions, and eight internal unidirectional plies of 145 g/mm³ in (45₂/-45₂)_s sequence. The matrix was HMF 934 epoxy resin.

In order to verify the cut quality, the top and bottom kerf width, the taper angle and the HAZ extension were measured by microscopic analysis as proposed by Tagliaferri et al. [7]. At the end, the kerf geometry and the HAZ were related to the process conditions. For each test condition, no less than fifteen profiles were analyzed.

Tab. I: Process parameters and beam properties used for the testing.

Duration (ms)	Lamp Voltage (V)	Frequency (Hz)	Mean Power (W)	Pulse Energy (J)	Pulse Power (kW)
1.00	420	100	69	0.69	0.72
	400	150	74,6	0.50	0.50
	400	200	65,8	0.33	0.33
0.50	600	150	89	0.59	1.19
	500	150	79,7	0.53	1.06
	500	200	73,8	0.37	0.74
0.25	700	150	95,7	0.64	2.55
	650	200	99,8	0.50	2.00
	650	250	92,2	0.37	1.48

Fig. 1. Schematic of pulsed laser cutting mechanism.

III RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

III.1 Cutting regions maps

In figure 2, a map of the cutting regions is reported. It delineates the “cut regime” and the “no-cut regime” for each adopted cutting condition as a function of cutting speed and beam mean power. The figure reveals that CFRP cutting is possible over a large

processing window enveloping a wide beam mean power-speed range. In the range of the adopted parameters, the maximum cutting speed is 11 mm/s obtained with a power of about 95 W. The figure also shows, that the maximum cutting speed (dashed line) that appears linear depends on the mean power.

As previously specified, the mean power depends on the pulse energy and the pulse frequency. In order to separate these parameters and to meaningful the effect of the spot overlap, a map was obtained also as a function of the pulse energy-spot overlap. The data are collected in figure 3, where the effect of the spot overlap and the pulse energy clearly appears. The latter plays a fundamental role in cutting mechanism: in fact, also in this case, a linear relationship between the minimum spot percentage and the pulse energy is observable, with the minimum spot overlap that decrease at the increase of the pulse energy, independently of the adopted mean power. The minimum value of the spot overlap is obtained in correspondence of the lower duration and the maximum pulse energy. Since both spot overlap and the pulse energy determine the cut performance, their influence on the cutting quality is also expected. To comprehensively analyze the impact of the process parameters on the cut quality, the kerf profile was analyzed for all the conditions reported in figures 3. The results are reported in the following section as a function of the spot overlap percentage.

III.2 Kerf Geometry

In figure 4 the typical kerf geometry is reported. In the figure, W_t , W_b and T_a are the top kerf width, the bottom kerf width and taper angle respectively, whit the taper angle calculated by the following expression:

$$T_a = \tan^{-1} \cdot \left(\frac{W_t - W_b}{2 \cdot t} \right) \quad 2)$$

where t is the sample thickness.

In figures 5 and 6 the mean values of fifteen measurements of the top and the bottom kerf width are plotted against the spot overlap. The vertical bars denote the standard deviations. The relationship between the kerf width and the process parameters is clear. Both the quantities show a similar trend, constant up to a spot overlap value of about 90%. Beyond this value, the top and the bottom kerf increase at the increasing of the spot overlap. However, the data distribution and the presence of data scattering do not allow any particular observation about the influence of the different values of pulse energy and pulse duration. Besides, the top kerf width appears always larger than the declared beam spot (min. 198 μm), while the bottom kerf width appears always lower then the top one, with minimum values smaller than the beam spot diameters (min. 68 μm against the 170 μm of the declared beam spot).

Knowing the top and the bottom kerf width, the taper angle was obtained and plotted against the spot overlap in figure 7. From the figure, the taper angle is very small, with values in the range of 1 ÷ 6 degree. It is about constant up to the value of 90 % of the spot overlap percentage, while for high values it tends to decrease. The aforementioned behaviours can be explained considering that at the increase of the spot overlap the interaction time increases, so more material is removed and a kerf more larger and regular is obtained, in agreement whit what observed by numerous authors [6-11].

Fig. 2: Influence of the mean power and beam speed on the cutting regions map. The dashed line represents the maximum cutting speed.

Fig. 3: Influence of the pulse energy and spot overlap on the cutting regions map. The dashed line represents the minimum spot overlap to cut.

Fig.4: Examples of kerf geometry (In the picture W_t is the top kerf width, W_b is the bottom kerf width, T_a is the taper angle and HAZ is the Heat Affected Zone extension).

Fig. 5: Top kerf width as a function of spot overlap for the different process parameters.

Fig. 6: Bottom kerf width as a function of spot overlap for the different process parameters.

Fig. 7: Taper angle as a function of spot overlap for the different process parameters.

III.2 Defect and HAZ extension.

The optical microscopy analysis showed the presence of thermal damage such as fibres debonding and matrix thermal degradation, while no delamination was observed.

In figure 8 the top and the bottom surface were reported as examples of the visual damage. In the figure the presence of matrix recession and burn, indicated by the arrow in fig 8A) are observable together with the fibre pull out. The damage extension decreases if the bottom side is considered, figure 8B), the latter appears about lacking in burn and only fibre pull out are visible. However, in both cases the damage appears very limited.

Despite the limited external HAZ, a larger HAZ extension could be occur in the centre of the thickness, as visible in figures 9A) and 9B) where two sections are reported for two different process parameters. In this cases the HAZ appears as matrix burning with or without the presence of inconsistent fibres. In order to assess the HAZ behaviours as a function of the process parameters the inner extension of the HAZ was measured and reported against the spot overlap and the cutting speed in figures 10 and 11 respectively. In figure 10, the continuous lines represent the best-fitting lines obtained following an exponential law for the three pulse duration values irrespective of the pulse energy. As expected, the HAZ extension is strictly related to the spot overlap and to the pulse duration increasing at the increase of both parameters.

About the HAZ it is useful to report also the results as a function of the cutting speed (figure 11). Figure 11 shows the influence of the cutting speed on the HAZ, increasing the cutting speed a linear decrease of the HAZ extension is obtained. In this case no particular influence of the pulse duration is observed.

III.3 Discussion

The foregoing results clearly show the importance of the pulse energy, pulse duration and pulse overlap selection on the cutting mechanism, therefore cutting speed is a practical parameter if the productivity is considered. It is possible to obtain material cut with different parameter combination and the cut quality depends on the adopted combination. An increase of the spot overlap produces an increase of the interaction time and of the released energy. Considering the minimum energy necessary to cut the laminate, a part of the extra energy is loss because passes through the kerf and another part is absorbed by the laminate. This last produces an enlargement of the kerf width, a more regular profile but also an increase of the HAZ extension. This phenomenon is amplified in the exanimate laminate by the presence of unidirectional lamina at the centre of the laminate because of the anisotropy of the local plies.

However, since the HAZ and the kerf width showed an energy release-time dependence a possible way to undertake, in order to improve both the productivity and the quality, is the use of short or very short pulse duration together with lower spot overlap. In fact, as observed in the present study, under these conditions, a sensible reduction of both HAZ and kerf width is obtained and if the same mean power is used no reduction of the cutting speed is necessary.

Fig. 8: Typical defect of the cut surface, A) fibre pull out and matrix degradation at the top side B) fibre bridging at the bottom side.

Fig. 9: Examples of the kerf section aspect, cut obtained for the process parameters: A) $E = 0.3 \text{ J}$, $D = 0.25 \text{ ms}$, spot overlap = 97%, B) $E = 0.6 \text{ J}$, $D = 0.25 \text{ ms}$, spot overlap = 83%.

Fig. 10: HAZ extension as a function of spot overlap for the different process parameters. The continuous lines represent the best-fitting lines obtained with an exponential law for the three pulse duration.

Fig. 11: HAZ extension as a function of cutting speed for the different process parameters. The line represent the best-fitting linear line of all the data.

IV CONCLUSIONS

In this work, features and the performances of a 100 W lamp pumped pulsed Nd:YAG laser in cutting of 1 mm in thickness CFRP laminates are presented. From the results, the following main conclusions were drawn:

- A pulsed Nd:YAG can be satisfactory used to cut CFRP plate 1 mm in thickness, at cutting speed of about 11 mm/s.
- Processing regimes for laser cutting can be established based on mean power and cutting speed or on the pulse energy and spot overlap parameters.
- The cutting tests showed that the maximum cutting speed depends on the released mean power, while the minimum spot overlap depends on pulse energy.
- Narrow kerf could be obtained reducing the spot overlap or increasing the cutting speed up to its limits. In this case the taper angle tends to increase up to 6 degree.
- The thermal damage consists of fibres debonding and matrix degradation, while no delamination was observed. The maximum HAZ extension occurs at the centre of the laminate in correspondence of unidirectional lamina.
- The HAZ extension is related to the spot overlap through an exponential law or to the cutting speed through a linear law.
- In correspondence of the same spot overlap, a reduction of the duration results in a lower HAZ extension.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are particularly grateful to the CIRTIBS Research Centre for the equipments and the financial support to develop the present research work.

References

1. Komanduri R., "Machining fibre reinforced composites", Mechanical Engineering, 1993, Vol. 27, pp. 58-64.

2. Koenig W., Wulff C., Grass P. and Willerscheid H., "Machining of Fiber Reinforced Plastics", *Annals of CIRP*, vol. 34 (2), 1985, pp. 537-548.
3. Koenig W. and Grass P., "Quality Definition and Assessment in Drilling of Fiber Reinforced Thermosets", *Annals of CIRP*, vol. 38 (1), 1989, pp. 119-124.
4. Tagliaferri V., Caprino G. and Diterlizzi A., "Effect of Drilling Parameters on the Finish and Mechanical Properties of GFRP Composites", *Int. J. Machine Tools Manufacture.*, 1990, Vol. 30 (1), pp. 77-84.
5. Caprino G; Tagliaferri V., "Damage development in drilling glass fibre reinforced plastics", *Int. J. Machine Tools and Manufacture*, 1995, Vol: 35 (6), pp. 817-829, ISSN: 0890-6955.
6. Tagliaferri V., "Laser cutting of reinforced materials", in: N.P. Cheremisinoff (Ed.), *Handbook of Ceramics and Composites*, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1990, pp. 451-467.
7. Tagliaferri V., Visconti I.C., "Machining of fibre reinforced materials with laser beam: cut quality evaluation", *Proceedings of European Conference on Composite Materials*, vol. 1, Elsevier, London, 1987, pp. 190-199.
8. Cenna A.A., Mathew P., "Analysis and prediction of laser cutting parameters of fibre reinforced plastics (FRP) composite materials", *International Journal of Machine Tools & Manufacture*, 2002, Vol. 42, pp. 105-113.
9. Mathew P., Goswami G.L., Ramakrishnan N., Naik N.K., "Parametric studies on pulsed Nd:YAG laser cutting of carbon fibre reinforced plastic composites", *J. of Materials Processing Technology*, 1999, Vol. 89-90, pp. 198-203.
10. Caprino G., Tagliaferri V., Covelli L., "Cutting glass fibre reinforced composites using CO₂ laser with multimodal-Gaussian distribution", *J. Mach Tools Manufacture*, 1995, Vol. 35, (6), pp. 831-840.
11. DI Ilio A., Tagliaferri V., Veniali F., Machining parameters and cut quality in laser cutting of aramid fibre reinforced plastics, *Mat. Manuf. Process.* Vol. 5 (4) (1990) 591-608.
12. Fenoughty K.A., Jawaid A., Pashby I.R., Machining of advanced engineering materials using traditional and laser techniques, *J. Mat. Proc. Tech.* 1994, Vol. 42 pp. 391-400.
13. Lau W.S., Lee W.B., Pulsed Nd:YAG laser cutting of carbon fibre composite materials, *Ann. CIRP* 39 (1) (1990) 179-182.
14. Chien C.Y., Gupta M.C., "Pulse width effect in ultrafast laser processing of materials", *Applied Physics A, Materials Science & Processing*, 2005, Vol. 81, pp. 1257-1263, ISSN: 0947-8396.
15. Yao Y.L., Chen H., Zhang W., "Time scale effects in laser material removal: a review", *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, 2005, Vol. 26 (5), pp. 598-608, ISSN: 0268-3768.
16. Morace R. E., Leone C., De Iorio I. "Cutting of thin metal sheets using Nd:YAG lasers with different pulse duration" *Proc. SPIE*, 2005, Vol. 6157, pp. 53-60, ISBN 0-8194-6206-3.